

Ways to Improve the Condition of Providing Trade Services to Rural Residents of Samarkand Region

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Abstract: This article examines the level of development of retail trade in the region, the retail turnover indicator per capita, the gross consumer spending indicator of the population, which reflects the socio-economic interests of consumers, the economic indicator of the activities of trade organizations, which reflects the economic interests of entities providing trade services, and private indicators of the provision of trade services.

Key words: Organization, trade, service, entity, activity, consumption, innovation.

Introduction. Currently, increasing and improving the quality of manufactured products, ensuring their stable sales in domestic and foreign markets, increasing their competitiveness in conditions of fierce competition, extending the life cycle of goods, creating new product projects based on market demand, strengthening the position of local goods, increasing their brand popularity, and providing services are considered to be urgent issues.

The main goal of the "Strategy for the Development of Competition in Commodity and Financial Markets for 2020-2024" set by our President is to stimulate economic growth and innovation, increase investment flows, and create new jobs by creating efficient markets and a healthy competitive environment. The creation of markets is also aimed at developing relations between economic entities.

Analysis of literature on the topic Based on foreign experience, it should be noted that many economists have been engaged in the development of marketing principles and their application in practice. Among them, we can include such famous scientists as F. Kotler, M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, D. Marshall.

While the research in the field of marketing conducted in our country for many years is based on national characteristics, it is also necessary to recognize the scientists who have made a significant contribution to the development of marketing theory in the economy. These include M. Mukhammedov, M. Pardaev, R. Ibragimov, YO. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhodjaev, B. Khodiev, D. Rakhimova, Sh. Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh. Musaeva and others.

Research methodology. The research process used a systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, and sample observation methods.

Research results. A comprehensive study of the state of the consumer market and the provision of trade services in rural areas was conducted based on data from the Samarkand region. In the course of the study, we studied and analyzed statistical data on the development of retail trade in the Samarkand region. Data from recent years show a steady increase in retail trade turnover per capita (Table 1). At the same time, it was observed that the annual growth rate of this indicator decreased during the studied period, since the average annual growth rate according to the forecast parameters of state programs is not less than 120%.

Table 1. Retail turnover per capita in Samarkand region in 2018-2023*

No.	Indicator name	2018	2019	2020	2022	2023
1	Total retail trade turnover per capita, thousand soums, including:	1151.3	1400.9	1698.3	2102.2	2446.5
	In the city	2398.4	3114.1	3917.8	4903.8	5860.4
	In the village	928.9	1129.5	1376.6	1656.2	1741.3
	Consumer Price Index	1,068	1,061	1,056	1,057	1,114
2	Growth rate of retail trade turnover per capita, in % compared to the previous year, including	114.2	113.9	114.8	117.1	104.4
	In the city	120.5	122.4	119.1	118.4	107.2
	In the village	115.2	114.6	115.4	113.8	94.4
3	The ratio of retail turnover per capita in urban and rural areas	2.6:1	2.75:1	2.84:1	2.96:1	3.36:1

According to the analyzed indicators, it was found that the rural population lags significantly behind the urban population. For example, retail turnover per capita in rural areas is 3.3 times lower than in urban areas. The analysis revealed significant differences in the provision of trade services across districts, which confirms the need for an individual approach to each district. Thus, one of the most important tasks of increasing the efficiency of trade services in rural areas is to eliminate the existing imbalance.

Solving this issue is associated, on the one hand, with the development of economic relations in the system of providing trade services, and, on the other hand, with the improvement of methodological aspects of assessing the effectiveness of trade services.

The first direction: is related to the improvement of the activities of trade entrepreneurship entities. We analyzed the distribution of retail turnover among entities providing trade services. The results of the research indicate an increasing role of dehqan markets and shopping complexes in the provision of trade services in the region, which account for 63% of the total volume of trade services. An in-depth analysis of various organizational forms of trade services allowed us to characterize their strengths and weaknesses and served as a basis for assessing the prospects for providing trade services to the rural population.

The need to improve the assessment of the level of trade services is due to the fact that in the current official statistical experience, only indicators of retail turnover and total trade services per capita are used.

As a scientific and methodological method for objectively assessing the level of trade services in rural areas of the republic, we have proposed a comprehensive approach. This approach takes into account the territorial, consumer and entrepreneurial aspects of the problem and reflects the complexity of trade service activities.

As a result of the research conducted, we found it necessary to include the following in the general indicators of the provision of trade services to the population:

- retail turnover per capita, reflecting the level of development of retail trade in the region;
- an indicator of the population's gross consumption expenditure, reflecting the socio-economic interests of consumers;

*Source: The table was compiled by the author from the Samarkand Regional Statistics Department (www.samstat.uz) and the official website of the Samarkand regional administration (www.samarkand.uz.) compiled on the basis of information.

- An economic indicator of the activities of trade organizations that reflects the economic interests of entities providing trade services.

In turn, each generalized indicator is composed of specific indicators of the provision of trade services, since their complexity does not allow them to be expressed in a single formula.

As a result of the theoretical and practical research conducted, we came to the conclusion that the level of provision of trade services in rural areas should be assessed through a system of indicators of various socio-economic nature (Figure 1).

Figure 1. System of indicators for assessing the effectiveness of providing trade services to rural residents

From an economic point of view, the use of this approach can serve as an objective assessment of the state of the existing system of trade services in rural areas. Based on this, it will be possible to identify socially necessary trade services, that is, to gradually move from the gross income of trade organizations to the elimination of subjective estimates of trade services provided, while simultaneously creating a favorable trading environment and incorporating services that study the needs of the population.

During the research, it became clear that today, insufficient attention is paid to the consumer aspects in assessing the effectiveness of providing trade services to the population. Clarification of the terms “consumer” and “buyer” is of scientific and methodological importance in revealing the features of the formation of the population's demand for goods. Ensuring consumer choice, that is, the availability of the opportunity to satisfy demand more effectively, forms the methodological basis of the consumer aspects of the assessment. At different stages of demand formation, the rural population plays different roles: including as a carrier of need, then as a buyer, and at the final stage as a consumer.

Dedicated to the development and scientific substantiation of strategic directions for improving the efficiency of trade services in rural settlements (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Strategic directions for improving the efficiency of providing trade services to rural residents

These areas include restructuring the system of providing trade services in rural areas, providing trade services, intensifying them, and updating their content. Each subsystem is aimed at fulfilling specific tasks to improve the level of satisfaction of the population's needs and the efficiency of retail trade.

The main source of increasing the efficiency of trade services is to increase the number of trade entities and strengthen their material and technical base. As data show, the level of provision of trade areas in rural areas is much lower than in urban areas. Therefore, prospective plans for the placement of retail entities remain a priority area for improving trade services to the population.

The factors influencing the provision of trade services to the rural population were studied, and the factors with a general impact reflect the level of development of the trade and consumer market in the region and have the same effect on all settlements. In our study, the impact of these factors was analyzed by determining the correlation between the factors with a general impact and the retail turnover per capita. The analysis showed that the impact of the factors with a general impact on the efficiency of trade services is low, which indicates the importance of the factors with a specific impact.

Today, a unique self-government body, the mahalla, has been formed in Uzbekistan, embodying the centuries-old traditions of the people and the processes of democratization of our society. The mahalla is not only a public organization aimed at solving social and household issues in a specific place of residence, but is also a public management body that contributes to improving the living standards of the population. The transfer of the main part of the powers from territorial state administration bodies to local self-government bodies serves to fully take into account the peculiarities of demand formation in individual places of residence.

The peculiarity of this system is that proposals come from neighborhood committees, as well as entrepreneurs and public organizations. As a result, the effectiveness of measures to provide trade services in individual settlements increases dramatically. The rapid development of trade activities requires the involvement of farmers' markets and trade complexes, unorganized trade entities in active efforts to meet consumer demand, that is, they must be transformed into modern structures

(for example, branch structures). In our opinion, the measures implemented within the framework of the Strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in five priority areas will allow the formation of a modern system of providing trade services in rural areas in 2019-2030

Figure 3. Retail structure based on e-commerce and improving the efficiency of rural trade services*

1 – personal visit to a trading company; 2 – order through communication channels; 3 – purchase (order fulfillment); 4 – order to replenish stocks; 5 – delivery of goods; 6 – contract for continuous replenishment of stocks; 7 – delivery of goods through a direct contract or dealer network; 8 – contract for the supply of agricultural products.

The study of the activities of retail trade organizations has shown the need to increase the efficiency of providing trade services to the population, attract investments in their material and technical base, strengthen the supply system of goods, and apply advanced trade technologies. In our opinion, this issue can be solved by attracting large urban trade enterprises to rural areas using economic and social means.

In addition, it is proposed to create legal conditions for the processes of mergers of private entrepreneurs. We propose to study and apply the experience of foreign countries in developing retail trade networks and supply cooperation. An important direction for increasing the efficiency of retail trade in rural areas is the formation of a mechanism for constantly improving the culture and quality of trade services. The basis of this mechanism is a strategy for improving the quality of trade services in the region in the future. The uniqueness of this strategy lies in taking into account the regional and local characteristics of retail development.

*Formed on the basis of the author's research.

Figure 4. Mechanism for continuous improvement of the quality of trade services to rural residents*

To improve the quality of service provision in trading enterprises in rural settlements, it is necessary to introduce technologies of trading processes and scientific methods of analyzing trade. The methodological basis of this direction is the development and implementation of standards for the provision of trade services in villages. Unlike retail trade rules, service standards reflect the obligations of a trading enterprise regarding the level of trade services. We propose to expand the scientific methods of retail trade by expanding forms of service provision outside the trading floor, expanding e-commerce methods, and introducing innovative regulatory mechanisms for the provision of services in retail enterprises.

Improving the culture of providing trade services requires that employees who work in rural areas have sufficient qualifications, therefore, we propose to form a system of training and retraining personnel in such areas as sales consultants, food sellers, non-food sellers, and sales agents. The implementation of the strategy for the accelerated development of trade services in rural areas will allow changing the ratio of trade services to the population in favor of rural residents.

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